

THE ROLE OF TASHKENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7179561>

Ne'matullayeva Nodirabegim Nodirovna

O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari talabasi

Ilmiy rahbar **Baxtiyarov Muxtorjon Yakubovich**

Abstract: *This article discusses the importance of Tashkent, it is one of the touristical cities of Uzbekistan, in the field of tourism.*

Keywords: *Tashkent, tourism, tourist city, historical monuments, Samarkand, Bukhara, handicrafts, history, capital*

Today, the Uzbek state cannot be imagined without tourism. Because the role of this industry in the potential of our country is invaluable. When we talk about tourism, first of all, we think of Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva, which are rich in historical monuments and sacred places. Because a lot of tourists organize a lot of tourist trips to the above-mentioned cities, and of course we can meet and communicate with them a lot. However, we can say without hesitation that Tashkent, the capital of our country, has achieved a lot in the field of tourism, not lagging behind these historical cities. The city of Tashkent stands out among the regions of the republic for its history and position as a center. When we start talking about the history of each city, first of all, our first president Islam Karimov; The phrase "there is no future without historical memory" in "Invincible Power of High Spirituality" comes to mind. Because when we always talk about a city, we can't help but look at its history, because the lessons we learn from the past draw the necessary conclusions for our future [1-7].

The word "Tashkent" itself means "stone city", and we can say that the history of the city is reflected in this word, but we all know that Tashkent is a very ancient city. lum. Stone Age artifacts have been found in the city; Bronze mirrors found in one of Tashkent's cemeteries, as well as coins from different countries, indicate that the city has a history of more than 2,000 years. The first sources on the history of Tashkent date back to the first centuries AD. In particular, we can see that the Greek scholar Ptolemy in his book "Guide to Geography" gave information about Tashkent. In Ptolemy's work, 26 maps of Central Asia and its environs are shown on 26 maps of the prosperous part of the globe, the oikumena. This map shows the trade route to China, east of the Yaksart (Syrdarya) basin; Terry Lapedia. Scholars have translated the Greek name "Stone Fortress" and named it after Tashkent. The name of the city of Tashkent appears in written sources in the forms Choch, Chochistan, Shosh, Shoshkent. The word "hair" also means "stone" in Sogdian. Shosh is the Arabic form of the name Choch. Shosh or

Choch means Tashkent and its environs. The Hududul Alam (Boundary of the

Worlds), written in Persian by an unknown author in the 10th century, states: "Chach is a large province, its people are warlike, rich and generous. There will be archery. The capital of Binkat-Choch. It is a large city, at the same time the residence of the king. "Mahmud Kashgari in his famous work mentions the name of Tashkent along with Shosh. In particular, he wrote in his "Qanuni Masudi": "Binkat is the capital of Shosh, in Turkish" Tashkent ", translated from Greek into Arabic -" Burjul Hijara "(" Stone Tower "). Beruni's claims have been confirmed by other scholars. For example, Mahmud Qashqari wrote in his Devonu lug'otit turk: "The name of Tarkan-Shosh, his real name is Tashkent, means a city built of stone." This means that the name of our capital "Tashkent" first appears in Beruni's works, and the city is called by other names [8-14]. The city of Chach, which was part of the Karakhanids, was completely renamed Tashkent in the late tenth and early twelfth centuries. During the reign of Amir Temur, a powerful fortress restored its status as a major city of handicrafts, culture and science, trade and commerce. At the beginning of the 16th century, Tashkent became part of the Shaybanid state, after which it became part of the Bukhara Emirate. At the end of the 15th century, in the 16th century and later in the 18th century, the status of Tashkent increased significantly. The economic and cultural boom was due to the revitalization of the city's ties with other craft and trade centers, as well as the development of construction. Large madrassas, such as the Barakkhan Madrassah and the Kokaldosh Madrassah, were built in the 16th century during the reign of the Uzbek sultans. We can see that these buildings have survived to this day. As early as the 16th century, Tashkent was a densely populated city, with a large number of merchants and artisans. Many coppersmiths, as well as potters, craftsmen who made various fabrics and clothes, weapons and other items, lived and worked here [15-20].

The center of Tashkent's life is the Chorsu Bazaar, which is visited by traders from different cities and countries. Chorsu is a unique town with specialized handicraft stalls, surrounded by caravanserais, bathrooms, kitchens and shops. The city's largest bazaar began on the streets that connected it, lined with shops and handicrafts on either side of the street. Basically the same goods were sold in every part of the market. There was a coat market under the tim in Khadra. There were caravanserais in and around the city, and merchants from different countries landed here. Tashkent, with some 60,000 caravanserais and a population of about 60,000, was second only to the khanate's capital in importance. Due to the deterioration of Kokand-Russia relations, Tashkent became of great strategic and economic importance, subordinating the entire Turkestan region, border fortresses and Turkestan, Shymkent and other cities.

No matter how many difficulties and hardships, the hard days of our people's courageous struggle are a testament to the fact that we live in peace and tranquility today. In any case, our hardworking people were digging pools and wells in some places in the city because of the war and the flooding [21-26]. The warm climate, fertile soil and irrigation system, as well as the hard work of the population, created favorable conditions for growing abundant crops in orchards and melons. Yards in areas with

plenty of water were reminiscent of cool, shady gardens, and trees and flowers were a boon to the yard. Tashkent grows grapes, peaches, apricots, plums, black and yellow figs, pomegranates, apples, pears, quinces, cherries, almonds and pistachios. Horticulture was an ancient tradition and at the same time a lucrative business - fruits were marketed and fruit peels were exported. The people of Tashkent took care of the trees, reaped a bountiful harvest, and created wonderful new varieties of fruit.

When we're talking of the history of Tashkent, we can say without hesitation that it has maintained its name in every era, even in various difficult situations, and today is a city that has achieved its success and is developing. After all, today's innovations, amenities and all other innovations are aimed at further developing our city and making a great impression on visiting tourists, as well as meeting their needs based on our own conditions. It is obvious that the reforms being carried out in Tashkent, the capital of our country, not only serve our people, but also provide a favorable opportunity and a wonderful view for tourists visiting our country.

Today, the construction of high-rise and luxury buildings is popular all over the world, and the buildings being built in our city are not inferior to those being built in developed countries. All this is to increase the number of tourists visiting our country and make them enjoy the unique beauty of our capital. Among them we can say "Tashkent city", "Magic city". They are built on the basis of perfect plans in all respects, so that the visiting tourists have the opportunity to see everything they want to see. In addition, today, every tourist traveling around Tashkent can get an interesting impression, because the streets of Tashkent are well-lit, bright and hospitable. You will be happy to see the prosperity and cleanliness of our city, because in some countries, despite the fact that it is developed in certain areas, the cleanliness of the city creates some inconvenient conditions for visitors. And in our country, all this is the service of workers who work around the clock in "Improvement". I think that the tourists who visit will also pay attention to the improvement of the streets of our city, so a lot of attention will be paid to the improvement of the capital. The most important thing is that the nature of our country, which is always in the spotlight of tourists, is second to none. In our capital, everything is in harmony. It should also be noted that the attention paid to tourists can be seen in the airports where they take their first steps.

When it comes to hotels that are important for tourists, first of all, we should mention the hotels in Tashkent. After all, the most comfortable and fully equipped hotels in the country have been built in our capital. These include the most popular hotels today, such as HILTON, GRAND MIR HOTEL and SIMMA. As for the hotels in Tashkent, there are many of them, but they have not been operating for a long time, and in a short period of time they have been able to meet all the needs of their guests. is becoming one of the hotels in service. Visiting tourists also return home with special impressions from this hotel. This process, of course, will play an important role in further developing the tourism potential of the capital. Currently, a lot of work is being done throughout the country to train leading personnel in the field of tourism. Today, in order to further improve the tourism system, young professionals are gradually

discovering new aspects of this direction, as well as focusing on increasing the tourism potential of the industry in our country, using foreign experience. In particular, it is easier to realize these opportunities in Tashkent. Because the level of language skills of young people can be quickly developed through communication when tourists visiting the capital on foot through the streets of our city, it should be noted that the conditions created for young people learning the language in our capital are also different. Tourists also pay attention to the environment of our streets and people's relationships during the trip. For example, in order to be able to communicate with tourists on the streets, it is necessary to increase the language skills of our young people in order to give them a great impression. The fact that the capital is using modern and useful methods to further increase the potential of tourism and comprehensively improve this area is another evidence of the great attention paid to the tourism industry.

It is clear that only tourists come to mind when talking about tourism, but one of the most interesting situations is the process of communicating with tourists, telling them fluently in the language of tourists about the history of our country, our hardships in history. Especially when you take tourists on a trip around the capital and travel by train until the evening, when you see the streets of our city at night, you can enjoy the joy. Because our city will be even more beautiful in the evening, and it will be a pleasure to watch it. I think the role of tourism in the potential of our capital is invaluable; The streets, the culture of communication of young people, the wonderful places in our city - all this not only delights the tourists of the capital in all respects, but also determines the place of the republic among the regions. It is not enough to describe the beauty of our capital in words, because it is better to see these opportunities and all the conveniences with our own eyes. Wonderful conversations with tourists also happen on the streets of the capital by chance. As for the hotels in Tashkent, depending on the number of visits of guests and tourists, we can know their quality and all the conveniences. Also, all the meetings and foreign meetings in the capital will determine the scale of our city. Our capital has its own character and in the near future it will be able to compete with the capitals of developed countries.

In short, as large-scale reforms are being carried out in our country day by day, our country will soon reach the highest peaks and determine its tourist significance all over the world. We will achieve all this news with the young people who are growing up in our country, and, of course, the contribution of Tashkent, the capital of our country, will be invaluable. Tashkent is a convenient and heavenly city for all-round tourists.

REFERENCES:

1. G'ulomxasanov E., Sardor A., Dilnoza S. Onlayn Turizmning Jahonda Hamda O'zbekistonda Tutgan ORni Va Rivojlanishi //Барқарорлик ва Етакчи Тадқиқотлар онлайн илмий журнали. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 367-374.

2. G'ulomxasanov E., Abdullayev N., Madina L. Turizm Va Ta'lim: Holati Va Istiqboli //Барқарорлик ва Етакчи Тадқиқотлар онлайн илмий журнали. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 343-348.

3. Гуломхасанов Э. М., Каримов К., Лазизова М. РАЗВИТИЕ ЭКОНОМИКИ НА ТЕРРИТОРИИ БУХАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ ПОСЛЕ КРИЗИСА COVID-19 //Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 474-478.

4. Якубова, Ш. Ш. "МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ КАНАЛОВ ТРАНСМИССИОННОГО МЕХАНИЗМА ДЕНЕЖНО-КРЕДИТНОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ."

Ученый XXI века 8 (2018): 43.

5. Gulomkasanov E., Shukurova M., Elmurodov B. THE ROLE OF GUIDES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTERNATIONAL TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN //Збірник наукових праць SCIENTIA. – 2021.

6. Gulomkhasanov E. M., Bakhadir O., Madina L. DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN THE TOURISM SPHERE IN UZBEKISTAN //ПРОБЛЕМИ ТА ПЕРСПЕКТИВИ РЕАЛІЗАЦІЇ ТА ВПРОВАДЖЕННЯ МІЖДИСЦИПЛІНАРНИХ НАУКОВИХ ДОСЯГНЕНЬ. – 2021. – С. 24.

7. Berdimurdoyna, U. N., & Kizi, M. M. A. (2021). Theoretical Foundations of the Effectiveness of the Development of the Infrastructure of the Regional Labor Market. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCES, 2(7), 10-14.

8. Berdimuradovna, U. N. (2021, June). THE MECHANISM OF REGULATION OF SOCIAL LABOR RELATIONS IN THE INNOVATIVE ECONOMY. In E-Conference Globe (pp. 129-133).

9. Berdimuradovna, U. N., & Umarbek o'g'li, R. A. (2021, June). ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF SMALL BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY. In E-Conference Globe (pp. 66-73).

10. Berdimuradovna, U. N., & Sadinovich, B. S. (2021). PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS OF EMPLOYMENT OF THE POPULATION IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY. DEVELOPMENT ISSUES OF INNOVATIVE ECONOMY IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR, 79.

11. Улугмурадова, Н. Б., Мияссарова, М. А. К., & Рашидов, А. У. У. (2021). МЕҲНАТ БОЗОРИ ИНФРАТУЗИЛМАСИНИНГ САМАРАЛИ РИВОЖЛАНИШ ЙЎЛЛАРИ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(6), 808-819.
12. Улугмуродова, Н. Б. (2021). ИҚТИСОДИЁТНИНГ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯЛАНИШИ ШАРОИТИДА МЕҲНАТ БОЗОРИ ИНФРАТУЗИЛМАСИНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШ ЙЎНАЛИШЛАРИ. *Экономика и финансы (Узбекистан)*, (2 (138)), 53-60.
13. УЛУҒМУРОДОВА, Н. (2021). DIRECTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF LABOR MARKET INFRASTRUCTURE IN THE CONTEXT OF ECONOMIC TRANSFORMATION. *Экономика и финансы (Узбекистан)*, (2), 53-60.
14. Абдурахманов, К. Х., Кадилов, Ш. М., & Улугмурадова, Н. Б. (2021). СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В РЕГУЛИРОВАНИИ РЫНКА ТРУДА. In *EUROPEAN RESEARCH: INNOVATION IN SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGY* (pp. 11-18).
15. Berdimuradovna, U. N. (2021). YOSHLAR BANDLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(5), 423-432.
16. Bedimuradovna, U. N. (2021). RESEARCH PARK.
17. Улугмурадова, Н. Б. (2012). Исследование производительности труда в зависимости от социально-трудовых отношений на предприятиях малого бизнеса Самаркандской области. *Экономика. Управление. Право*, (8-2), 39-41.
18. Улугмурадова, Н. Б. (2012). Исследование производительности труда в зависимости от социально-трудовых отношений на предприятиях малого бизнеса Самаркандской области. *Экономика. Управление. Право*, (8-2), 39-41.
19. Berdimuradovna, U. N. Formation Of Labor Resources In The Field Of Small Business And Private Entrepreneurship. *JournalNX*, 126-128.
20. Berdimurodova, U. N. Theoretical Foundations of Labor Relations in the Field of Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship. *JournalNX*, 148-152.
21. Абдурахманова, Г. К., Кадилов, Ш. М., & Улугмурадова, Н. Б. (2021). ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ ПРОФЕССИЙ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ, НАИБОЛЕЕ ВОСТРЕБОВАННЫХ НА РЫНКЕ ТРУДА УЗБЕКИСТАНА. *Вестник науки и образования*, (8-1 (111)), 40-47.
22. Farkhod, M., Azadkhon, K., Gulkhon, M., & Oybek, A. (2020). Advantages of the transition to a digital economy in the innovative development of Uzbekistan. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, 12(6), 1226-1232.
23. Nazrullaevna, M. G. (2021). Mechanisms for the development and management of innovative activity in Uzbekistan. *SOUTH ASIAN JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT RESEARCH*, 11(4), 15-20.

24. Nazrullaevna, M. G. (2021). O 'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA KICHIK BIZNESNI

INVESTISIYALASHNING O 'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. *Oriental renaissance:*

Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 1(5), 640-645.

25. Мелибаева, Г. (2021). Иқтисодиётни диверсификациялаш шароитида тижорат банк активлари самарадорлигини ошириш масалалари. *Общество и инновации*, 2(4/S), 282-291.

26. Nazrullaevna, M. G. (2021). Management Mechanisms for Innovative Activities in Economic Systems. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS ON TOURISM MANAGEMENT AND FINANCE*, 2(11), 31-35.

